

Social Anxiety and Personality Traits as Predictors of Social Media Addiction among staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State University

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Abstract

Social media addiction is increasingly recognized for its psychological and socio-economic impacts, such as impaired social relationships, academic underperformance, anxiety, and depression. While research on this phenomenon is emerging in Nigeria, there remains a gap in understanding the predictive role of social anxiety, personality traits, and self-esteem, especially among workers and students in higher institutions. This study examines how social anxiety, personality traits and demographics (age and gender) predict social media addiction. This study addresses this gap by employing a cross-sectional quantitative survey with 397 participants in Plateau State. The study made use of the social cognitive theory to explain this phenomenon. Three Hypotheses were tested. Social anxiety did not significantly predict social media addiction ($\beta = .120$, $R^2 = .014$, $p > .05$), suggesting it has no influence in this context. Personality traits, however, were significant predictors ($R = .18$, $R^2 = .032$, $p < .05$), with extraversion ($\beta = .112$, $p < .05$) and conscientiousness ($\beta = -.106$, $p < .05$) having notable effects. Age and gender differences were non-significant (age: $F(3, 393) = .637$, $p > .05$; gender: $t(397) = 1.017$, $p > .05$). This study recommends tailored interventions, additional research, and application of findings in practice to better address social media addiction among Nigerian workers and students.

Keywords: Social Media Addiction, Social Anxiety, Personality Traits.

Introduction

Social media has significantly altered communication, information sharing, and global connectivity. Platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat, and TikTok are central to daily life, influencing interactions and self-perceptions. In 2021, 69% of adults in the U.S. used at least one social media platform, with growing usage across age groups (Auxier & Anderson, 2021). Globally, there are over 2.8 billion active social media users, spending more than two and a half hours daily on these platforms (Cao et al., 2020).

In recent years, social media has become an integral part of contemporary society, overcoming barriers of distance and time while transforming how people interact and organize their daily lives. It is based on values of transparency, personalization, user-driven communication, collaboration, and the sharing of information and knowledge (Cheng et al., 2021). Social media encompasses online platforms and applications that allow users to create, discuss, alter, and share content created by others. These platforms are rooted in the technological and conceptual foundations of Web 2.0 (Mahamid & Berte, 2019).

Social media encompasses a variety of platforms such as business networks, blogs, podcasts, and e-commerce sites (Gong et al., 2020). Users can be categorized based on behavioral factors like trust and control, with different types of personalities influencing their involvement on

these platforms (Nwafor et al., 2023). Understanding these behaviors is important for examining how personality traits impact social media participation.

While social media offers numerous benefits in everyday life, its extensive use has raised concerns about its effects on mental health and overall well-being. In particular, social media use and addiction have been found to be particularly high in African regions compared to others (Aygul & Akbay, 2019). One key issue is social media addiction, which is defined as a condition where individuals are unable to control their behaviors and impulses, leading to significant disruptions in daily functioning (Bloemen & De Coninck, 2020). Social media addiction, also known as problematic social media use or social media dependency, is defined by the excessive and compulsive engagement with social media platforms, which leads to negative impacts on various aspects of life. This addiction can result in reduced productivity, damaged relationships, and harmful psychological effects. Social media addiction is considered a form of internet addiction and is categorized as a behavioral addiction. It involves uncontrollable use of social media, disrupting daily functioning and preventing individuals from effectively managing routine tasks (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013).

Social media addiction, driven by the pleasure of interaction and rewards like comments and feelings of belonging, can lead to psychological dependence (Ejaz et al., 2020). This dependency becomes particularly dangerous if social media is the primary source of self-worth, potentially resulting in negative effects like rejection, isolation, depression, or even suicidal thoughts if lost (Stănculescu & Griffiths, 2022).

Social media addiction, especially among adolescents and young adults, is a growing concern due to its negative impacts, such as poor mental health and lower academic performance in university students (Abbott, 2021). This has prompted further investigation into the causes and consequences of the phenomenon. Social media addiction among students is often linked to the Fear of Missing Out (FoMO), particularly among adolescents and young adults who want to stay updated with trends and events within their peer groups (Costa et al., 2019; Sun & Zhang, 2020). While environmental factors are significant in the development of addiction, internal factors may also contribute to this issue (Zubairu, 2021). This research therefore explores such factors.

Social anxiety, or social phobia, is a psychological condition characterized by a strong fear of social interactions, especially with unfamiliar people, due to the fear of being negatively evaluated. Anxiety, in general, is an uncomfortable feeling of apprehension triggered by uncertain threats (Michael, 2024). This study views social anxiety as a continuum, where individuals with higher levels of anxiety fear judgment and rejection in social situations (Mohammadi et al., 2020). Such individuals may turn to social media to avoid direct interactions, potentially increasing their risk of social media addiction (Ejaz et al., 2024).

Personality is a multifaceted characteristic that defines an individual. Given the wide range of theories on the subject, it lacks a single, universal definition (Stănculescu & Griffiths, 2022). Therefore, it is often most effectively understood through the identification of traits (Mohammadi et al., 2020). Personality traits are stable and enduring characteristics that shape an individual's thoughts, emotions, and behaviors (Zubairu, 2021). This research defines personality as a collection of relatively consistent traits over time, measured through frameworks like the Big Five model (McCrae & Costa, 1987), which includes Openness,

Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism, abbreviated as OCEAN (Stănculescu & Griffiths, 2022).

Personality traits such as extraversion, neuroticism, and conscientiousness are linked to social media addiction. Extraverts may use social media for social interaction, while individuals with high neuroticism may turn to it for emotional coping. Those with low conscientiousness may engage in impulsive behaviors, including excessive social media use (Stănculescu & Griffiths, 2022).

Objective of the Study

The study investigates how social anxiety, personality traits (extroversion, introversion, and neuroticism), and demographic factors (age and gender) contribute to social media addiction. It aims to assess the relationships between these variables and their influence on the likelihood of developing addictive social media behaviors.

Research Questions

1. What is the connection between social anxiety levels and the risk of developing social media addiction?
2. Are certain personality traits more closely linked to social media addiction?
3. Do age and gender play a role in influencing social media addiction?

Methodology

Research Design

The cross-sectional survey research design was used in this study.

Research Setting

The population of this study comprised of staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State Polytechnic.

Sample Size

The sample size for this study was calculated using the Krejcie and Morgan table, resulting in approximately 379 participants. To account for potential drop-offs, the researcher distributed 400 questionnaires, and 397 were successfully returned for data analysis.

Sampling Technique

The study employed a Convenience sampling technique to represent sample from the target population.

Ethical consideration

The front page of the questionnaire included a consent form that outlined the rights of the participant.

Data Analysis

The study tested hypotheses using Regression Analysis, ANOVA, and T-Test, with data analyzed through SPSS version 24 software.

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 1a: Socio Demographic Information of Respondents (n = 397)

Institution	Frequency	Percent
University of Jos	266	67.0
Plateau State Polytechnic	131	33.0
Age		
18-20 years	79	19.9
21-30 years	295	74.3
31-40 years	19	4.8
41-50 years	4	1.0
Gender		
Female	227	57.2
Male	170	42.8
Religion		
Christianity	366	92.2
Islam	31	7.8

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2024

The study’s respondents were mostly from the University of Jos (67%), with 33% from Plateau State Polytechnic. The majority were female (57.2%) and aged 21-30 years (74.3%). Most participants were Christian (92.2%), with a smaller percentage practicing Islam (7.8%). The age range of respondents varied from 18 to 50 years, and the gender distribution was 42.8% male.

Table 1b: Socio Demographic Information of Respondents (n = 397)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Parents' employment status		
Unemployed	59	14.9
Self-employed	208	52.4
Government Institute	94	23.7
Private Institute	36	9.1
Family type		
Polygamy	113	28.5
Monogamy	284	71.5
Parents’ marital status		
Married	353	88.9
Divorced	21	5.3
Separated	23	5.8

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2024

This presents the demographic details of the respondents, including their parents' employment status (52.4% self-employed, 23.7% in government, 9.1% in private institutions, and 14.9% unemployed). Most respondents come from monogamous families (71.5%) and have married parents (88.9%).

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Social anxiety will significantly predict social media addiction among staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State Polytechnic was analyzed using regression analysis as shown below:

Table 2: Summary of linear regression showing influence of social anxiety on social media addiction

Model		SS	df	MS	R	R ²	F	P
1	Regression	405.574	1	405.574	.057	.003	1.269	> .05
	Residual	126257.908	395	319.640				
	Total	126663.481	396					

Dependent Variable: Social media addiction

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2024

The findings show that social anxiety does not significantly affect social media addiction ($\beta = .120, R^2 = .014, F(1, 395) = 1.269, P > .05$). This suggests that social anxiety among staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State Polytechnic does not predict social media addiction. As a result, hypothesis one is rejected.

Hypothesis Two: Personality traits will significantly influence social media addiction was analyzed using regression analysis as shown below:

Table 3: Summary of multiple regression showing influence of personality traits on social media addiction

Predictors	B	T	P	R	R ²	F	P
Extraversion	-.112	-2.064	< .05				
Conscientiousness	-.106	-1.906	< .05	.180 ^a	.032	2.579	< .05
Agreeableness	.011	.179	> .05				
Neuroticism	.041	.696	> .05				
Openness	-.072	-1.216	> .05				

Dependent Variable: Social media addiction

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2024

The study found that personality traits collectively predict social media addiction, explaining 3.2% of the variance. Specifically, higher extraversion predicts lower addiction levels, and higher conscientiousness predicts lower addiction levels. However, agreeableness, neuroticism, and openness do not significantly influence social media addiction. Thus, hypothesis two is partially supported.

Hypothesis Three: Demographic variables (age and gender) will significantly influence social media addiction among staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State Polytechnic. The result is presented in the following tables.

Table 4: Summary of One-Way ANOVA showing difference between age groups on social media addiction

	SS	df	MS	F	P
Between Groups	612.593	3	204.198	.637	> .05
Within Groups	126050.889	393	320.740		
Total	126663.481	396			

Dependent Variable: Social media addiction

Source: Author’s Fieldwork, 2024

The results show that age does not significantly affect social media addiction among staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State Polytechnic as there was no significant difference observed across age groups.

Table 5: Summary of t-test of independent showing difference between male and female on social media addiction

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	T	p
Social media addiction	Female	227	91.36	18.99	395	1.017	> .05
	Male	170	89.51	16.28			

The results show no significant difference in social media addiction between female and male participants, with both groups exhibiting similar levels of addiction. Therefore, hypothesis three is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one, which proposed that social anxiety would significantly influence social media addiction among staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State Polytechnic, was not supported by the findings. Unlike previous studies, such as those by Uchegbu et al. (2021), which found a significant relationship between social anxiety and social media addiction in a similar demographic, this study found no such connection. The discrepancy may be due to factors like sampling methods, data collection tools, or social desirability bias.

Hypothesis two proposed that personality traits will significantly predict social media addiction. The results confirmed that personality traits had a significant joint effect on social media addiction, with extraversion and conscientiousness showing independent influence, while agreeableness, openness, and neuroticism had no significant impact. This finding aligns with some past studies, such as those by Andrews et al. (2020) and Illies et al. (2020), which reported that all five personality traits significantly influenced social media addiction. Overall, personality traits play a key role in predicting social media addiction and other internet-related issues.

Hypothesis Three, which proposed that age and gender would significantly influence social media addiction, was not supported by the findings of this study. Unlike previous research by Uchegbu et al. (2021), which showed that females were more susceptible to social media addiction, the current study found no significant impact of age or gender. The authors recommend further research with more advanced data collection methods and varied demographics to better understand these results.

Conclusion

This research utilized a cross-sectional approach to investigate the influence of social anxiety and personality traits on social media addiction among staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State University. Three hypotheses were tested, each corresponding to a research question. The results indicated that social anxiety had no impact on the social media usage of the participants, whereas personality traits, in combination, significantly influenced the likelihood of social media addiction. The study examined the impact of social anxiety and personality traits on social media addiction among staff and students in University of Jos and Plateau State Polytechnic. It found that social anxiety did not significantly influence social media use, but personality traits, particularly extraversion and conscientiousness, had a notable effect. Higher extraversion increased vulnerability to social media addiction, while higher conscientiousness acted as a protective factor. Traits like agreeableness, openness, and neuroticism showed no significant influence. Additionally, age and gender were not significant predictors. The study calls for further research to explore these factors across different demographic groups to better address social media addiction.

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